

Occurrence of the viable population of *Chasmina candida* (Walker, 1865) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Bagisarinae) on Praslin Island, Seychelles

Ivan N. Bolotov*, Vitaly M. Spitsin, Yulia S. Kolosova & Artem A. Frolov

Institute of Ecological Problems of the North,
Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Northern Dvina Emb., 23,
163000 Arkhangelsk, RUSSIAN FEDERATION

*corresponding author: inepras@mail.ru

Introduction

The “large white” group of noctuids, belonging to the genus *Chasmina* Walker, 1856, includes at least fifteen virtually pure white species that are difficult to separate (Holloway 1989; Barnett *et al.* 1999). *Chasmina candida* (Walker, 1865) is a moderately rare species that is widely distributed in the Indo-Australian tropics to the east of Fiji, including many islands of the Indian Ocean and Pacific (Robinson 1974; Holloway 1989; Barnett *et al.* 1999). The northernmost species records are known from southern Japan (Kishida 2006). Usually, this species is observed in coastal areas, therefore, a recently published record from the mainland India may be erroneous (Gurule & Nikam 2013).

Only *Hibiscus tiliaceus* L. and *Thespecia populnea* (L.) Sol. ex Corrêa (Malvaceae) are listed as valuable host plants for *C. candida* larvae (Gerlach & Matyot 2006; Leong 2010; Robinson *et al.* 2010). Both of these plant species are inhabitants of coastal ecosystems of mainland and oceanic islands, including beach crests and mangroves. Some authors noted that *C. candida* is associated with mangroves (Veenakumari & Prashanth 2009; Leong 2010). But, on the Fiji islands, the species is found in areas of secondary vegetation (Robinson 1974). Leong (2010) provided a description of the last instar larva and data on the species biology in Singapore.

The species is rare in all known localities, and from each locality only a few specimens were recorded (Holloway 1989; Veenakumari & Prashanth 2009; Leong 2010; Sivaperuman & Shah 2012). On oceanic islands, *C. candida* is most widespread in the Fiji archipelago, where it was found on the two major islands, Viti Levu and Vanua Levu, and on four smaller islands (Robinson 1974). In the Seychelles islands, a few specimens were collected from Praslin and Mahé islands, but they were not recorded there since 1960 (Gerlach & Matyot 2006). On Praslin Island, *C. candida* was known from a single record in 1905. The conservation status of the species in the Seychelles was not exactly determined, due to deficiency of reliable data (Gerlach & Matyot 2006).

Material and methods

This note is based on the field observations effected in January 2013 at Anse Possession, Praslin Island. During evening and night time periods, we recorded the moth

specimens that were attracted to the light of electric lamps of hotels and local houses located in the coastal lowland area. A few specimens of *C. candida* were selectively collected for morphological study. The materials (eight pinned specimens) are deposited in the Biological Museum of the Institute of Ecological Problems of the North of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Arkhangelsk city, Russia (INEP). Images of the specimens were recorded with a digital camera Canon EOS 60D. The dissection of the genitalia and male coremata was performed using standard methods for Lepidoptera. The abdomen was macerated in hot 10% KOH solution for 30 min. Then, genitalia and coremata were placed on the temporary slides with glycerin-ethanol solution, and photographed using the stereomicroscope Leica M165C. All images were processed with Adobe Photoshop CS version 8.0.

Results

Specimens collected. 5♂, 1♀, Seychelles: Praslin Island, Anse Possession [4°18'36"S; 55°43'45"E], alt. 5 m a.s.l., coastal lowland, at light, 5th–8th January 2013, I.N. Bolotov leg.; 1♂, 1♀, Seychelles: same locality, at light, 17th January 2013, I.N. Bolotov leg.

Imago habitus. The male forewing length is 14–16 mm (n = 6); it has a square appearance and the costa concave (Fig. 1a), which are the most distinctive features of the male morphology (Holloway 1989). The apex of the male forewing is square and acute. The female forewing length is 16–17 mm (n = 2); the forewing apex is rounded (Fig. 1b). Both sexes have a pure white marking on head, thorax, abdomen, legs, fore- and hindwings, except for the orange (“ochraceous” by the protologue of Walker (1865)) fore femora, tibiae and tarsi, with black dots on the anterior face of tibia and tarsus. Antennae are brownish or dark-yellow; palpi are white with orange tips. The external characters of the Praslin Island individuals are identical to the specimens collected from Borneo (Holloway 1989) and Singapore (Leong 2010), but differ slightly from the Fijian male specimen (Robinson 1974: Fig. 28), which has a more rounded apex of the forewing.

Genitalia. The male genitalia have a typical *Chasmina* pattern, the valves are apically rounded (Fig. 1c). Phallus is short, slightly curved dorso-ventrally and acuminate at the end (Fig. 1d). Male has a large coremata, paradorsally from the base of the eighth tergite (Fig. 1e). Robinson (1974), noted this structure as pair of bright mint-green “powder-puffs” [but, did he mean a living specimen] for, exclusively, diagnostic features of the species. It is strange that Holloway (1989) did not mention the coremata in his description of the *C. candida* male, but noted that coremata presents only in three other *Chasmina* species. In general, the male genitalia of specimens from Praslin Island are similar to those from the Fiji archipelago (Holloway 1989: 187, Fig. 358) and Japan (Kishida 2006: 284, Fig. 3). The female genitalia (Fig. 1f) are identical to those of specimens from the Cocos (Keeling) Islands of Australia (Holloway 1989: 187, Fig. 360).

Field observation data. This was a very common species at the locality during the period 4th–22nd January 2013. The individuals were recorded daily near the electric lamps of the Sea View Lodge Hotel and closest coastal local houses on the Anse Possession (Fig. 1g). Usually, 3–5 specimens were seen near each lamp per night (max. 10 ex., 17th January).

Figure 1. *Chasmina candida* (Walker, 1865): Seychelles, Praslin Island, Anse Possession, January 2013.
 a) Male specimen (upperside).
 b) Female specimen (upperside).
 c) Male genitalia (ventral view).
 d) Male phallus (lateral view).
 e) Male coremata (dorsal view, removed from the abdomen and straightened).
 f) Female genitalia (ventral view).
 g) Live male specimen attracted to light of a local house.
 h) Habitat of the population: beach crest on the Anse Possession with the host plant *Thespecia populnea* (L.) Sol. ex Corrêa (in the fore of the image).

Moreover, the species was the most abundant representative among Macrolepidoptera during the observation period. All discovered specimens were clean or little damaged, which indicated their local emergence (see Fig. 1g).

Habitat and expected range of population. The discovered population inhabited a narrow beach crest at Anse Possession and adjacent capes, where there is a different type of coastal ecosystem, associated with sandy and rocky sites, and freshwater stream mouths. Sparse mixed forests with bush patches are the most widespread community in this area. The common plant species are *Calophyllum inophyllum* L. (Calophyllaceae), *Terminalia catappa* L. (Combretaceae), *Heritiera littoralis* (Dryand.) Aiton. (Malvaceae), *Casuarina equisetifolia* L. (Casuarinaceae), *Cocos nucifera* L. (Arecaceae), *Cordia subcordata* Lam. (Boraginaceae), *Scaevola taccada* (Gaertn.) Roxb. (Goodeniaceae). *Thespesia populnea* is the most abundant of the two larval host plants of *C. candida* on Anse Possession; it is distributed in small patches along the seashore (Fig. 1h). We estimated that the area of occupancy of the moth population is restricted to a small site (ca. 1.5 km length, 50 m width), which has an area of approximately 0.075 km².

Discussion

Specimens of *C. candida* were absent in the samples of comprehensive surveys of many Seychelles islands that were provided as part of the Indian Ocean Biodiversity Assessment 2000-2005 (Gerlach & Matyot 2006). The species was not observed on Cousine Island (Lawrence 2005) which is situated at ca. 5 km SW from Praslin Island. Woods (2013) actively studied Lepidoptera for the period 9th April to 13th September 2013 at the site of a former leper colony, on the south coast of Curieuse Island, which is located in front of Anse Possession, with a minimal distance between them of only 2–2.5 km. *C. candida* specimens were also not recorded. Thus, the Anse Possession population is local, and specimens were not found in other areas, including the nearest islands. The host plant *Thespesia populnea* within patches on the seafront are the main source for existence of the moth population (see Fig. 1h).

The species life cycle is poorly studied but, usually, imagoes were observed in January, including our data, with samples from the Andaman Islands (Veenakumari & Prashanth 2009) and Singapore (Leong 2010). The last instar larva of the species collected in Singapore was pupated on 19th May and imago emerged on 31st May (Leong 2010).

With respect to our data, the Seychelles population of *C. candida* can be categorised as Vulnerable (D1 – small population, D2 – restricted range). Anse Possession does not belong to protected areas, and the species population may be threatened after construction of hotels and local houses, that may decrease the host plant abundance.

Acknowledgements

This study has been partially supported by grants of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (№12–P–5–1014) and the Ministry of Science and Education of Russia. We are thankful to O.S. Pokrovsky (France) and Mrs. G. Lablache de Charmoy (Seychelles) for some practical arrangements.

References

- Barnett, L. K., C. W. Emms & J. D. Holloway. (1999) The moths of the Chagos Archipelago with notes on their biogeography. *Journal of Natural History* **33** (7): 1021–1038
- Gerlach, J. & P. Matyot. (2006) *Lepidoptera of the Seychelles islands*. Backhuys Publishers, Leiden, 130 pp.
- Gurule, S. A. & S. M. Nikam. (2013) The moths (Lepidoptera: Heterocera) of northern Maharashtra: a preliminary checklist. *Journal of Threatened Taxa* **5** (12): 4693–4713
- Holloway, J. D. (1989) The Moths of Borneo: family Noctuidae, triline subfamilies: Noctuinae, Heliiothinae, Hadeninae, Acronictinae, Amphipyriinae, Agaristinae. *Malayan Nature Journal* **42**: 57–226.
- Kishida, Y. (2006) Description of a new species of the genus *Chasmina* Walker, 1856 (Noctuidae: Bagisarinae) from the Ogasawara Islands. *Japan Heterocesis' Journal* **241**: 283–284.
- Lawrence, J. M. (2005) The Lepidoptera of Cousine Island, Seychelles. *Phelsuma* **13**: 94–101
- Leong, T. M. (2010) Final instar caterpillar and metamorphosis of *Chasmina candida* (Walker, 1865) from Singapore (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Bagisarinae). *Nature in Singapore* **3**: 211–215
- Robinson, G. S. (1974) Macrolepidoptera of Fiji and Rotuma: a taxonomic and biogeographic study. Durham theses, Durham University, <http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/8237>
- Robinson, G. S., P. R. Ackery, I. J. Kitching, G. W. Beccaloni & L. M. Hernández. (2010) HOSTS – A Database of the World's Lepidopteran Hostplants. Natural History Museum, London, <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/hosts> [Accessed 19.i.2014]
- Sivaperuman, C. & S. K. Shah. (2012) Diversity of moth in Great Nicobar Biosphere Reserve (GNBR), Andaman and Nicobar Islands. *Biological Forum* **4** (1): 23–26
- Veenakumari, K. & M. Prashanth. (2009) A note on the entomofauna of mangrove associates in the Andaman Islands (Indian Ocean: India). *Journal of Natural History* **43** (13-14): 807–823
- Walker, F. 1865. *Arbasera candida*. List of the specimens of lepidopterous insects in the collection of the British Museum **32**: 638–639
- Woods, P. J. (2013) The Lepidoptera of Curieuse Island, Seychelles. *Phelsuma* **21**: 58–64

First record and distribution of *Heliotropium curassavicum* L. (Boraginaceae) in the Mascarene Islands

KERSLEY PYNEE* AND DAVID H. LORENCE**

*The Mauritius Herbarium, Agricultural Services, Ministry of Agro-Industry and Food Security, Réduit, Mauritius. [kpynee@mail.gov.mu]

**National Tropical Botanical Garden, 3530 Papalina Road, Kalaheo, HI 96741, USA. [lorence@ntbg.org]

Abstract: *Heliotropium curassavicum* L. is documented for the first time as a naturalized species on Mauritius, Mascarene Islands.

Heliotropium L. (Boraginaceae) consists of 280 to 350 species of herbs, shrub, lianas and small trees from the temperate and warm regions of the world, mostly in arid zones (Feuillet & Bosser 2005; Mabberley 2008). Only three species, namely *H. arborescens* L., *H. indicum* L., and *H. amplexicaule* Vahl were previously recorded in the Mascarene Islands of Mauritius, Réunion, and Rodrigues (Feuillet & Bosser 2005).

In Réunion, *H. arborescens*, an introduced species originally from Peru, is cultivated in gardens as ornamental and was at times used to prepare perfume. *Heliotropium indicum*, a Brazilian species, is present in all three islands where it is considered as invasive alien and is mostly found in the lowlands, in crop vegetation, or abandoned lands. *Heliotropium amplexicaule*, another South American species, is absent in Rodrigues but is considered as an alien weed in sugarcane plantations in both Mauritius and Réunion. We here document the first occurrence of *Heliotropium curassavicum* L. as a naturalized species on Mauritius. In the Mascarenes this introduced coastal exotic species has been documented only from Mauritius and appears to be absent from both Réunion and Rodrigues.

Heliotropium curassavicum is a perennial herb with a native range from the southern United States through the Caribbean islands to South America, various Pacific islands including Hawaii, and westward to Australia where it is considered to be indigenous (Craven 1996; Wagner *et al.* 1999). It is also introduced and naturalized in S. Europe and in some tropical and subtropical regions of the Old World including parts of Africa (Martins 1990; Satyavani *et al.* 2013). It is a halophyte mostly found growing in coastal saline or alkaline soils (McAuley 2007). *Heliotropium curassavicum* has been traditionally used to treat wounds and diseases like rheumatism (Kirtikar & Basu 1998), and it has been also tested against cancer and diabetes (Sharma *et al.* 2009).

Heliotropium curassavicum was collected by the first author in 2005 near the Port-Louis harbor (K. Pynee s.n. in MAU 0012274). On 18th of January 2005, at Mer Rouge, next to the Free Port of Mauritius (Baie du Tombeau side, 20°08'14"S,

57°29'54"E; 1 m altitude) his attention was drawn to an unusual species of Boraginaceae, growing in association with native species including *Sesuvium ayresii* Marais (Aizoaceae), *Sporobolus virginicus* (L.) Kunth (Poaceae), and *Zoysia matrella* (L.) Merr. (Poaceae), and also, exotics such as *Commelina benghalensis* L. (Commelinaceae) and *Tribulus cistoides* L. (Zygophyllaceae).

At first sight, the small prostrate plant with glaucous fleshy leaves and tiny white flowers had the general appearance and physiognomy of *S. ayresii* (Aizoaceae) which was recorded there before (K. Pynee s.n. in MAU 0012461). On closer inspection, the plant's terminal spicate inflorescence with flowers grouped in small cymes confirmed that it belonged to the Boraginaceae family. Identification was undertaken at the Mauritius Herbarium (MAU), using the Flore des Mascareignes (Bossier and Feuillet 2005) and other literature available, and also comparing with all Boraginaceae herbarium samples. However, the specimen could not be assigned to any Boraginaceae known from the Mascarenes. During the visit of the second author to the herbarium in November 2008, however, the species was identified and determined as *Heliotropium curassavicum* L.

On 29 March 2012 a second population of *H. curassavicum* was discovered and a herbarium specimen collected (K. Pynee s.n. in MAU 0009289). The population consisted of 15 small clumps, growing on exposed sand dunes at Baie du Cap, at the entrance of Macondé Mining Company (20°29'13"S, 57°21'47"E, 9 m altitude). The

Fig. 1. *Heliotropium curassavicum* at Baie du Camp

low, prostrating and spreading plants with succulent leaves ranged from 10 to 15 cm in height. Green immature fruits together with small white bell-shaped flowers were present in double rows on curled inflorescences. Other species growing in association were *Dactyloctenium ctenoides* (Steud.) Bosser (Poaceae), *Phyla nodiflora* (L.) Greene (Verbenaceae), and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. (Poaceae).

This species was likely introduced into Mauritius unintentionally via equipment or freight. Based on its halophytic characteristics and habitat preferences, this naturalized species may occur on other islets or outer islands, mainly on seaside or on sand dunes should be sought when surveying these areas.

References

- Craven, L.A. 1996. A taxonomic revision of *Heliotropium* (Boraginaceae) in Australia. *Australian Syst. Bot.* **9**: 634-635.
- Feuille, C. & Bosser, J. 2005. 126. *Boraginacées*, pp. 1-39. In: Bosser J. & Guého J. (Eds.), Flore des Mascareignes - La Réunion, Maurice, Rodrigues. 121. Apocynacées à 126. Boraginacées. Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Paris; Mauritius Sugar Industry Research Institute, Ile Maurice; The Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, pp. 91-95.
- Kirtikar, K.R. & Basu, B.D. 1998. *Indian Medicinal Plants*. 2nd Ed., International Book Distributors, Dehradun, India, pp. 804-806.
- Mabberley, D.J. 2008. *Mabberley's Plant-book: A Portable Dictionary of Plants, their Classification and uses*. Third Edition. Cambridge University Press.
- Martins, E. S. 1990. Boraginaceae. *Flora Zambesiaca* **7**(4): 59.
- McAuley, M. 2007. *Plant of the Month: Wildflowers of the Santa Monica Mountains*. Santa Monica Mountains Trails Council, Agoura Hills, California.
- Padya, B. M. 1984. The climate of Mauritius. Meteorological office, Mauritius.
- Satyavani, K., Dheepak, V., Gurudeeban, S. & Ramanathan, T. 2013. Direct organogenesis of Seaside Heliotrope (*Heliotropium curassavicum*) using stem explants. *Pakistan J. Biol. Sci.* **16**: 1216-1219. **DOI**: 10.3923/pjbs.2013.1216.1219
- Sharma, R.A., Singh, B., Singh, D. & Chandrawat, P. 2009. Ethnomedicinal, pharmacological properties and chemistry of some medicinal plants of Boraginaceae in India. *J. Med. Plants Res.* **3**: 1153-1175.
- Wagner W. L., Herbst D.R., & Sohmer S.H. 1999. *Manual of the Flowering Plants of Hawai'i*. 2 vols. University of Hawai'i Press & Bishop Museum Press, Honolulu, 1-1853.

First record of *Sceliphron madraspatanum* (Fabricius, 1781) (Hymenoptera: Sphecidae) from the Malagasy subregion

Michael Madl

2. Zoologische Abteilung, Naturhistorisches Museum
Burgring 7, 1010 Wien, Austria
michael.madl@nhm-wien.ac.at

The genus *Sceliphron* Klug, 1801 is known from all zoogeographical regions. In the Malagasy subregion it is represented by the endemic species *Sceliphron fuscum* Klug, 1801, which is recorded from Seychelles (Mahé, Silhouette, Praslin, Aldabra), Comoros (Anjouan, Mohéli), Mayotte, Madagascar, Réunion and Mauritius (Madl, unpublished catalogue of the Sphecidae of the Malagasy subregion). It has been accidentally introduced into New Caledonia. Although *Sceliphron fuscum* has been recorded from New Caledonia several times, there are no recent records (Madl, unpublished catalogue of the “Sphecoidea” of New Caledonia). I failed to collect *Sceliphron fuscum* there in 2009.

Sceliphron madraspatanum (Fabricius, 1781) is widely distributed in the Oriental, Palaearctic and Australian regions and has been split in several subspecies (van der Vecht & van Breugel 1968). The material contains the nominate subspecies. Currently *Sceliphron madraspatanum* is widely distributed in Mauritius (Madl, unpublished data).

Material examined: Vacoas: Henrietta 3 ♀♀ December 2003 leg. Siedlecki – Savanne: Souillac 2 ♀♀ January 2004 leg. Siedlecki.

The material is deposited in the Natural History Museum in Vienna, Austria.

Acknowledgements

I am indebted to Owen Griffiths (Owner of the “La Vanille Réserve des Mascareignes” in Rivière des Anguilles, Mauritius) for the donation of the material to the Natural History Museum and Manuela Vizek (Natural History Museum Vienna, Austria) for her various help in preparing this paper.

References

Vecht, J. van der & Breugel, M. A. van 1968: Revision of the nominate subgenus *Sceliphron* Latreille (Hymenoptera, Sphecidae) (Studies on the Sceliphronini, part I). *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie* **111** (6): 185-255.

The Coco-de-Mer abroad – notes supplementary to Fauvel’s 1915 monograph

Anthony S. Cheke
139 Hurst Street, Oxford OX4 1HE, UK
anthony.cheke@dodobooks.com

Before the discovery of living Coco-de-Mer *Lodoicea maldivica* palms on Praslin in by Barré in 1768, the nuts were washed up on Asian shores, primarily the Maldives, and acquired a medicinal reputation and fabulous prices due to their rarity, erotic shape and mysterious origin (Fauvel 1915, Lionnet 1970, McAteer 2001). Later, once the price bubble had been burst by the Indian market being flooded with fresh nuts by French-Mauritian sea-captain Jean Duchemin in 1769, there was nonetheless an ongoing demand for the hard shells to make containers (Fauvel 1915, Lionnet 1970) – even today they can sometimes be seen in use in temples in southern India (pers. obs. 1981). Medicinal and culinary use, apparently of smuggled nuts, continues in China (Mak & Mok 2011), and unworked whole Coco-de-Mer nuts (*Lodoicea maldivica*) now sell for up to £562 in London auctions (e.g. in January 2014, <http://www.bonhams.com/auctions/21325/lot/239>). Recent studies have concentrated on the palm’s biology and conservation (e.g. Gerlach 2003, Rist *et al.* 2010).

Fauvel’s rarely-read 138-page study contains a very complete bibliography of the Coco-de-Mer up to 1906 when his work was completed; Lionnet’s booklet is in essence a very condensed version of Fauvel’s work, with some updating.

Medicinal uses in the 17th century

Early European writers were generally more struck by the nuts’ rarity and monetary value than the medicinal uses of the kernel, it being generally rather vaguely referred to in the 16th and 17th centuries as good against poisons and venereal disease (Fauvel 1915). However John Marshall’s detailed description from his travels 1668-1672 was not published until 1927 (Khan 1927), so unknown to Fauvel. Given its date, the detail of how the medication was prepared, and the rarity of Khan’s book, Marshall’s text is reproduced here, in his original orthography:

Coco Maldivica

Coco Maldivica or Sea Cocho is found upon the Maldiva islands and is there cast up by the Sea. It is supposed to grow upon a tree in the sea, so that when it is ripe, the strength of the water breaks it from the branch on which it growes. It is much like other Coconutt, only bigger. Tis a Sovereign Antidote against poison, being ground upon a Stone and a little water put to it and drunk. Tis also very good against fevers, being drunk with water, and for Agues drunk with Arrack. The usual way is to take the Nut and rub it upon a stone, and putting a littel water upon it, untill you have rubbed of[f] such a quantity as will make white and as thick as milk a quarter of a

pint of water. Then put into said quantity of water and drink it of[f], going to bed or keeping warme after it. But if for an Ague, instead of water, take Arrack, Brandy or Sack. The greater the distemper is, the greater quantity must be taken. This nut is very deare. I have paid for [a] peece of its Kernell 4 times its weight in Rupee silver for it.

[from Harleian MS 4254, folio 15 (British Library); Khan (1927), p.331]

Muslim water and alms bowls

Crooke (in Yule & Burnell 1903) noted that “the hard shell is largely used to make Fakirs’ water bowls” and Fauvel (1915) expanded on the use of partial nuts as drinking vessels by mendicant fakirs in India and Persia (Iran), some intricately carved. Lionnet (1971) added that nuts exported ‘until recently’ “made fakir’s bowls and were also used by pilgrims to Mecca to eat their food, since these pilgrims are supposed to use only utensils produced by nature”. ‘India’, pre-1947, included the what are now the largely Muslim countries of Pakistan and Bangladesh.

Travelling recently in Turkey, I was surprised to find a half-nut displayed in the museum in Konya dedicated to the Sufi poet Jalāl ad-Dīn Rumi and his order of whirling dervishes (Figs 1 & 2). The misidentified nut, dated as 19th century, bears the following label: “Keshkül, which means bowl of the poor, is made from a large coconut, cut from its upper side, carved and chained from both ends. There are some bowls made from metals such as silver or copper keeping its unique form”. There is no indication of how these nuts reached Turkey (and the museum clearly confused them with coconuts *Cocos nucifera*), but they were possibly acquired in Mecca from Indian pilgrims.

Fig.1. Dervish alms bowl made from half a coco-de-mer nut in the Rumi museum, Konya, Turkey; to the right is part of a silver bowl made in a similar style [author’s photo].

Fig.2. The same nut seen from above – from a photo on the museum’s information panel.

References

- Fauvel, A.A. 1915. Le Cocotier de mer des Seychelles (*Lodoicea seychellarum*). *Ann. Mus. Colon. Marseille* (3)3: 169-307.
- Gerlach, J. 2003. Pollination in the Coco-de-Mer, *Lodoicea maldivica*. *Palms* 47(3): 135–138
- Khan, S.A. (ed.) 1927. *John Marshall in India. Notes and observations in Bengal*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 471pp.
- Lionnet, [J.F.]G. 1971. *Coco-de-Mer. The romance of palm*. [no place of publication, ? Mahé, Seychelles]: author. 46pp.
- Mak, Chun-yin & and Mok, Chuen-shing. 2011. Molecular identification of *Lodoicea maldivica* (coco de mer) seeds. *Chinese Medicine* 2011: 6: 34 -doi:10.1186/1749-8546-6-34.
- McAteer, W. 2001. *Rivals in Eden. The history of the Seychelles 1742-1827*. Rev. ed. Mahé, Seychelles: Pristine Books, 314pp.
- Rist, L., Kaiser-Bunbury, C.N., Fleischer-Dogley, F., Edwards, P., Bunbury, N. & Ghazoul, J. 2010. Sustainable harvesting of coco de mer, *Lodoicea maldivica*, in the Vallée de Mai, Seychelles. *For. Ecol. Manage.* 260: 2224–2231.
- Yule, H. & Burnell, A.C. 1903. *Hobson-Jobson. A glossary of colloquial Anglo-Indian words and phrases, and of kindred terms, etymological, historical, geographical and discursive*. 2nd ed. [with additional notes by W.Crooke]. London: John Murray. 1021pp. [reprinted 1979, New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal].

Distribution and habitat of the invasive giant day gecko *Phelsuma grandis* Gray 1870 (Sauria: Gekkonidae) in Reunion Island, and conservation implication

Mickaël Sanchez^{1,*} and Jean-Michel Probst^{1,2}

¹ Nature Océan Indien, 6, Lotissement les Magnolias, Rivière des Roches, 97470 Saint-Benoît, La Réunion, France

² Nature et Patrimoine, 2, Allée Mangaron, Dos d'Ane, 97419 La Possession, La Réunion, France

* Corresponding author; e-mail: natureoceanindien@gmail.com

Abstract. The giant day gecko *Phelsuma grandis*, endemic to Madagascar, was introduced to Reunion Island (Indian Ocean) in the mid-1990s. No studies have been conducted so far to define its precise distribution and habitat. To fill the knowledge gap about this invasive species, we compiled available data and performed field work during 2007-2014. We detected 13 distinct populations of *P. grandis*, occurring mainly in the northern part of Reunion Island and on the west coast. This gecko inhabits human disturbed areas (gardens, urban parks, bamboos, orchards, coconuts, and banana plantation) and secondary habitats (shrubby savanna, and secondary dry woodlands, secondary dry and wet thickets). Its distribution strongly suggests that saltatory dispersal (through deliberate and/or accidental transport) and natural colonization are the mechanisms of spreading through Reunion Island. All our data in combination with both *P. grandis* ecology and native environmental range suggested that this gecko may colonize native forest, and constitutes a potential important threat to the native biodiversity of Reunion Island (arthropods and lizards).

Key words. *Phelsuma grandis*, Reunion Island, distribution, invasive species, conservation.

Introduction

Day geckos of the genus *Phelsuma* are distributed in the western Indian Ocean (Austin *et al.* 2004). This group is monophyletic and contained at least 52 species (Rocha *et al.* 2009; 2010; Uetz 2013). *Phelsuma* species are colorful, attractive lizards and represent one of the most popular Gekkonidae group for herpetoculturists. The international trade has induced many introductions in several countries of the world (Lever 2003; Mozzi *et al.* 2005; Cheke & Hume 2008; Cole 2009; Kraus 2009; Krysko *et al.* 2011; Meshaka 2011). The giant day gecko *Phelsuma grandis* Gray, 1870 is the perfect illustration of this phenomenon. Native to the north of Madagascar, this species has been reported to be a successful invader in different environments. Additionally, available literature indicates that *P. grandis* constitutes an important threat to native fauna and lizards in particular (Allison 2002; Krysko *et al.* 2003; Cole 2009; Sanchez & Gandar 2010a; Sanchez & Probst 2012; Dervin *et al.* 2013; Buckland *et al.* 2014).

On Reunion Island, the first invasive population of *P. grandis* was reported in

the mid-1990s (Probst 1997a). The tropical climate and a broad range of habitat have probably facilitated its establishment. Due to the potential negative impact on endemic threatened geckos (i.e. *P. inexpectata* Mertens, 1966 and *P. borbonica* Mertens 1966, respectively considered as Critically Endangered and Endangered (IUCN France & MNHN 2010)), since 2012 French law prohibits introduction and trading of all *Phelsuma* species in Reunion Island. The administrative destruction of *P. grandis*, *P. laticauda* (Boettger, 1880) and *P. madagascariensis* Gray, 1831 is also allowed. However, the ecology and distribution of *P. grandis* are poorly known on Reunion Island: only few data are published and no precise distribution map is currently available. The aim of this study is to fill the knowledge gap about habitats and distribution of *P. grandis* on Reunion Island.

Materials and methods

Study area

Together with Mauritius and Rodrigues, Reunion Island belongs to the Mascarene archipelago (Indian Ocean). Located 800 km east of Madagascar, it is an oceanic volcanic island. Dramatic topographical changes have generated numerous and diverse ecosystems, from the lowland xeric forest (western part, leeward side) to the lowland rain forest (eastern coast, windward side), through tropical mountain cloud forest. In contrast to Mauritius and Rodrigues where less than 1 % of the original vegetation still remains (Strahm 1996), original habitats are still well preserved on approximately 30 % of the surface of Reunion Island. The native vegetation is found at higher elevations (> 1000 m) and scarcely in lowland natural habitats (Strasberg *et al.* 2005).

Study species

Phelsuma grandis is an arboreal and diurnal gecko. In its native range, it inhabits secondary habitats (various plantations and orchards, palms or buildings), primary rainforest and deciduous dry forest (Glaw & Vences 2007; D’Cruze *et al.* 2009). The dorsal colour patterns consist of red spots on a brightly green background. Males have a larger size, a larger head and are more colourful than females (maximum total length 300 mm) (Wanger *et al.* 2009a; 2009b) (Fig. 1). Immatures (total length 65-70 mm) are also different from adults by exhibiting a dorsal pattern with more colour spots. Like other *Phelsuma* species, this species is territorial (Demeter 1976; Krysko *et al.* 2003). The diet consists of arthropods, snails, others geckos, plant resources such as floral nectar, fruits and seeds (Demeter 1976; Tyle 1992; Probst 1999; Dervin *et al.* 2013; Minnaar *et al.* 2013). On Reunion Island, *P. grandis* shows an opportunistic foraging behaviour by consuming a wide range of prey (Dervin *et al.* 2013).

Data collection and field sampling

To determine species distribution, precise geographic data (i.e., referring locality and/or GPS coordinates) were first compiled from literature (Girard 1997; Probst 1997a; 1997b; 1999; Deso 2001; Probst *et al.* 2002; Sanchez & Probst 2012). Dubos (2013) described a new introduced population in Manapany-les-Bains, but this population was

Fig. 1. The giant day gecko *Phelsuma grandis* on Reunion Island. A: male; B: female; C: immature.

eradicated in 2010 (Sanchez & Gandar 2010a; 2010b). As a consequence, these obsolete data from Dubos (2013) were excluded from our compiled dataset.

From 1996 to 2006, opportunistic observations were performed and were also included in our data. During 2007-2014, we recorded all data from local environmental services (naturalists, local NGO, etc.), and field oriented researches were performed, focusing nearby known sites of species distribution and on sites with doubtful observations. We surveyed suitable micro-habitats (eg. palm species, *Pandanus* thicket) during daytime for at least 20 minutes (list of surveys in Appendix I). Geckos were detected on visual cues using binoculars (10x42). For each observation, we collected different information: date, site, coordinates (UTM40S-WGS84 system), elevation, hour, sex and age, activity (e.g., insolation, movement, and alimentation), micro-habitat (plant or artificial structure), plant species used and natural habitat (according to Dupont *et al.* 2000). Our observations were divided in two age classes based on estimated total length of the gecko (TL<10 cm for immature; TL >10 cm for adult). Gender was distinguished using external sexual characters (hemipenal bulges and anofemoral pores for male, developed endolymphatic chalks sacs for female). In the field, we also collected data from testimonies of local person, notably information about the origin and the introduction date of this species.

Data analysis

Data are classified into two categories: (1) site where a breeding population

is established (with breeding clue and/or with several individual from different sex), name “population” and (2) site where the establishment of a breeding population is not confirmed (only one gecko and no breeding clue), name “station”. Two sites separated from at least 1 km were considered as two distinct populations. Geographical data were mapped on a metric square grid (1 km²) using QUANTUM-GIS (Q-GIS 2013).

Results

A total of 170 records of *P. grandis* were gathered, 1 from literature, 7 collected opportunistically before 2007, 138 from field study performed between 2007 and 2014, and 24 from environmental services. From 2007 to 2014, we carried out 74 hours of surveys during which we counted 193 geckos, wherein 30 males, 26 females, 87 unsexed adults, and 50 immatures.

The distribution map of *P. grandis* on Reunion Island is shown in Figure 2. We identified 13 populations of this gecko, mainly occurring in the north and in the west coast (Table 1). Populations are distributed between 0 m and 600 m a.s.l. The largest population is localized in the north (Population n°11, “Niagara”, Table 1) and corresponds to the first known introduction point on the island (Probst 1997a). Besides, 12 stations are identified, 9 in the north and 3 in the south. One station is in Saint-Joseph district, within the distribution area of the endemic Manapany-day-gecko (*P. inexpectata*).

Fig. 2. Distribution map of *Phelsuma grandis* on Reunion Island. Black numbers refers to the population described in Table 1. Green square: breeding population; Yellow square: station; Black line: district limits.

Fig. 3. Habitats occupied by *Phelsuma grandis* in Reunion Island: A: bamboos; B: coconuts; C: shrubland savanna; D: secondary dry thickets.

Table 1. List of population of *Phelsuma grandis* on Reunion Island. Latitude and longitude are given in Universal Transverse of Mercator system (UTM, map datum: WGS84).

District	Lat.	Long.	Elevation (m)	Habitat	Introduction date	Origin	Sources
1 Condé Saint-Pierre	345166	7644235	380	Garden	<2009	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
2 Université du Tampon	345245	7647209	530-570	Garden, urban park	<2001	Unknown	G. Deso pers. comm,
3 Le Plateau, Saint-Leu	326148	7651656	310	Garden	<2009	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
4 Hermitage, Saint-Paul	315665	7667982	10	Garden, urban park	<1999	Deliberate introduction from Madagascar?	Probst et al. 2002;
5 Bellemène, Saint-Paul	322973	7674611	370	Garden	<2009	Deliberate introduction of unknown origin	Testimony collected in field
6 Cambaie, Saint-Paul	323431	7681156	100	Garden	<1999	Unknown	Probst et al. 2002;
7 Lataniers, Possession	328000	7683327	40-300	varied*	<2001	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
8 Montgaillard, Saint-Denis	340336	7688015	130	Garden	<2009	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
9 Grande Montée, Sainte-Marie	346480	7685272	240	Garden	<2010	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
10 La Ressource, Sainte-Marie	347352	7684393	320	Garden	<2010	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
11 Niagara, Sainte- Suzanne Saint-André	356478	7685519	0-250	varied*,	1994 (first observation on Reunion Island)	Voluntary release by reptile breeder	Probst 1997a
12 Palmiers Royals Saint-Benoit	365357	7673873	50	Garden	<2009	Unknown	Testimony collected in field
13 Chemin Mirabelle, Petite-Ile	351832	7638295	340	Garden	<2012	Unknown	Testimony collected in field

* varied = garden, bamboo, orchads, shrublands savanna, secondary dry thickets and woodland

Phelsuma grandis inhabits different types of habitats on Reunion Island (Fig. 3): human perturbed areas as gardens, urban parks, bamboos, orchards, coconuts, and banana plantation, as well as secondary and disturbed habitats, as shrubland savanna (dominated by *Pithecellobium dulce* and *Albizia lebbek*), secondary dry thickets (dominated by *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Litsea glutinosa* and *A. lebbek* or dominated by *Schinus terebinthifolius* and *Furcraea foetida*), secondary dry woodlands (dominated by *P. dulce*) and secondary wet thickets (dominated by *Syzygium jambos*). Most populations are located in urban areas (mainly in gardens), but two populations (Lataniers, n°7 and Niagara, n°11, Fig. 2, Table 1) are both urban areas and disturbed natural habitats (shrubland savanna, secondary thickets and woodlands).

Phelsuma grandis were observed on plant species and artificial structures (mainly on concrete wall and posts). Bamboos (*Dendrocalamus giganteus*), *Pandanus* sp., coconuts (*Cocos nucifera*), and others palm species (*Dypsis lutescens*, *Phoenix* sp., *Ravenala madagascariensis*, *Roystonea* sp., *Veitchia merrillii* and non-identified palm species) were the most frequently recorded plant species, followed by fruit trees (*Carica papaya*, *Litchi chinensis*, *Mangifera* sp.) and various other taxa (e.g., *A. lebbek*, *Calophyllum inophyllum*, *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Coccoloba uvifera*, *Dracaena* sp., *Eucalyptus* sp., *Furcraea foetida*, *Heliconia* sp., *Hiptage benghalensis*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Litsea glutinosa*, *Musa* sp., *Pithocellobium dulce*, *Saccharum officinarum*, *Senna* sp., *Schinus terebinthifolius*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Terminalia catappa* and non-identified plants species).

Discussion

Phelsuma grandis on Reunion Island was first recorded in 1994 (Probst 1997a), but the number of introduction events from Madagascar, or from reptile nurseries, is unknown. In this study, 13 breeding populations are identified, mainly distributed in the northern and western part of the island. The broad pattern of distribution and the number of populations suggest that multiple and independent introductions from Madagascar or from existing populations on Reunion Island are probably common. Moreover, *P. grandis* can be transported accidentally over vast distances. “Vehicular-rafting” could be an important diffusion agent for geckos (Gill *et al.* 2001; Norval *et al.* 2012), and presumably for *P. grandis* in particular (Deso 2001). Additionally, dissemination (eggs and geckos) can also occur by transporting plants and materials (pers. obs. J.-M.P. & M.S.). The number of stations without observed breeding (n=12) could be explained by these saltatory dispersal processes.

Phelsuma grandis inhabits only disturbed habitat, outside of native forest. It has a wide range of habitats, but it mainly occurs in human-disturbed habitats. Two populations, initially restricted to urban area (e.g., Lataniers, n°7 and Niagara, n°11; Probst 1997a; Probst *et al.* 2002), are now distributed in disturbed natural habitats (shrubland savanna, secondary thickets and woodlands), suggesting range expansion through natural colonization. The presence of viable populations in these kinds of habitats in combination, with the native environmental ranges of *P. grandis* in Madagascar (i.e., primary rainforest and deciduous dry forest) point out that this invasive gecko could colonize native forests of Reunion Island. Given the *P. grandis* diet, and that the

proportion of endemic species of arthropods and terrestrial snails increases related to the level of preservation of the habitats (Quilici et al. 2002; Ledoux 2004; Griffith & Florens 2006; Ledoux 2007; Attié et al. 2008; Martiré & Rochat 2008), this invasive species may have an important negative impact on these fauna groups.

As observed in its native range (Van Heygen 2004; D’Cruze *et al.* 2009) and other invaded countries (Florida, Bartlett & Bartlett 1999; Krysko & Hooper 2006; 2007; Mauritius, Cole 2009), *P. grandis* frequently uses bamboos, coconuts, fruit trees and others palm species. These habitats are similar to those where the native geckos (*P. inexpectata* and *P. borbonica*) have been reported (Sanchez *et al.* 2009; Sanchez 2012). Except for the station discovered within the distribution area of the endemic *P. inexpectata* (despite several field searches, occurrence of a breeding population is not proven), the distribution of *P. grandis* does not overlap with the distribution of native day geckos. In case of sympatry with native geckos, given the similarity in ecological preferences, behaviour, diet, and larger size, the invasive species may increase the inter-specific competition for space and food resources (plant and animal). Also, direct predation (observed on several geckos included *Phelsuma* sp.; Cole 2009; Buckland *et al.* 2014) might lead to the sharp decline of native geckos. On Mauritius, Buckland *et al.* (2014) have shown that native *Phelsuma* sp. suffer from the presence of *P. grandis* (strong decrease in abundance and local extinction), but causes leading to the decline are not clearly identified.

By providing a precise picture of the distribution of *P. grandis* on Reunion Island, this study is a critical step in the Regional Management Plan (Sanchez 2013) defined (1) to control the expansion of *P. grandis* through the island and (2) to avoid settlement of this invasive species in natural areas where it could directly threaten the native fauna, notably day gecko species. In order to complete these objectives, several actions (e.g., communication toward general public and conservation workers, and population control) are in progress or will be conducted during the coming years. The former natural colonization and saltatory dispersal suggest that the spread of *P. grandis* will continue on Reunion Island: this species will probably established viable populations in native forests and in the range of native day geckos. Given its potential negative impacts, it is crucial to take dispersal process into consideration (saltatory dispersal and natural colonization) for the management of this invasive species.

Acknowledgements

The study was supported by the Direction de l’Environnement de l’Aménagement et du Logement de La Réunion. We would like to thank all those who have sent us their observations and helped us in the field. Also, we particularly thank Christopher J. Raxworthy for useful comments about species ecology on Madagascar, Timothée Le Péchon and Johanna Clémencet who helped us with English translation and commented on an earlier version of the manuscript.

References

Allison, A. (2002) New record of *Phelsuma madagascariensis* in Hawaii. Available at: http://www.phelsumania.com/public/artoc/es/biogeography_hawaii.html. Last accessed on 13 August 2013.

- Attié, M., T. Bourgoïn, J. Veslot & A. Soulier-Perkins. (2008) Patterns of trophic relationships between planthoppers (Hemiptera: Fulgoromorpha) and their host plants on the Mascarene Islands. *Journal of Natural History* **42** (23-24): 1591-1638.
- Austin, J.J., E.N. Arnold & C.G Jones. (2004) Reconstructing an island radiation using ancient and recent DNA: the extinct and living day geckos (*Phelsuma*) of the Mascarene islands. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* **31**: 109-122.
- Bartlett, R.D. & P.P. Bartlett. (1999) *A Field Guide to Florida Reptiles and Amphibians*. Gulf Publishing Company, Houston, Texas, USA, 278 pp.
- Buckland, S., N.C. Cole, J. Aguirre-Gutiérrez, L.E. Gallagher, S.M. Henshaw, A. Besnard, R.M. Tucker, V. Bachraz, K. Ruhomaun & S. Harris. (2014) Ecological Effects of the Invasive Giant Madagascar Day Gecko on Endemic Mauritian Geckos: Applications of Binomial-Mixture and Species Distribution Models. *Plos One* **9**(4). doi e88798.
- Cheke A.S. & L. Hume. (2008) *Lost Land of the Dodo. An Ecological History of Mauritius, Réunion & Rodrigues*. T & Ad Poyser ed., London, 464 pp.
- Cole, N.C. (2009) *A Field Guide to the Reptiles and Amphibians of Mauritius*. Defra's Darwin Initiative & Mauritian Wildlife Foundation, Mauritius, 80 pp.
- D'Cruze, N., J. Sabel, J. Dawson & S. Kumar. (2009) The influence of habitat type and structure on the abundance of *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis* (Gekkonidae) in northern Madagascar. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* **4**: 55-61.
- Demeter, B.J. (1976) Observations on the care, breeding and behaviour of the giant day gecko *Phelsuma madagascariensis* at the National Zoological Park, Washington. *International Zoo Yearbook* **16**: 130-133.
- Dervin, S., S. Baret, L. Penin & M. Sanchez. (2013) Régime alimentaire du grand gecko vert de Madagascar, *Phelsuma grandis* Gray, 1870 (Squamata : Gekkonidae) sur l'île de La Réunion. *Cahiers Scientifiques de l'océan Indien occidental* **4**: 29-38.
- Deso, G. (2001) Note sur le transport insolite de geckos verts, le cas du *Phelsuma inexpectata*. *Bulletin Phaethon* **13**: 56.
- Dubos, N. (2013) New locality record for *Phelsuma grandis* (Sauria: Gekkonidae) in Reunion, in sympatry with the critically endangered *Phelsuma inexpectata*. *Herpetology Notes* **6**: 309-311.
- Dupont, J., D. Strasberg & J.-C. Rameau. (2000) Typologie des Milieux Naturels et des Habitats de La Réunion. Version 2010 modifié par F. PICOT et M. SALIMAN. DIREN Réunion/Université de La Réunion, 27 pp.
- Gill, B.J., D. Bejakovtch & A.H. Whitaker. (2001) Records of foreign reptiles and amphibians accidentally imported to New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology* **28**: 351-359.
- Girard, F. (1997) Présentation des espèces du genre *Phelsuma* vivant sur l'île de La Réunion. *Bulletin de la Société Herpétologique de France* **84**: 55-56.
- Glaw, F. & M. Vences. (2007) *A Field Guide to the Amphibians and Reptiles of Madagascar*. 3rd Edition, M. Vences & F. Glaw Verlag, Germany, 495 pp.

- Griffiths, O.L. & F.B.V. Florens. (2006) *A field guide to the non-marine molluscs of the Mascarene Islands (Mauritius, Rodrigues and Réunion) and the Northern Dependencies of Mauritius*. Bioculture Press, Mauritius, 185 pp.
- IUCN France & MNHN (2010) La Liste rouge des espèces menacées en France. Premiers résultats pour la faune de La Réunion. Dossier de presse. 1 July 2010. MNHN, IUCN France, 26 pp.
- Kraus, F. (2009) *Alien Reptiles and Amphibians. A Scientific Compendium and Analysis. Series: Invading Nature - Springer Series in Invasion Ecology Vol. 4, Germany*, 564 pp.
- Krysko, K.L., J.P. Burgess, M.R. Rochford, C.R. Gillette, D. Cueva, K.M. Enge, L.A. Somma, J.L. Stabile, D.C. Smith, J.A. Wasilewski, G.N. Kieckhefer, M.C. III Granatosky & S.V. Nielsen. (2011) Verified non-indigenous amphibians and reptiles in Florida from 1863 through 2010: Outlining the invasion process and identifying invasion pathways and stages. *Zootaxa* **3028**: 1-64.
- Krysko, K.L. & A.N. Hooper. (2006) *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis* (Madagascar Giant Day Gecko). Nectarivory; Potential pollination. *Herpetological Review* **37**(2): 226.
- Krysko, K.L. & A.N. Hooper. (2007) Potential Pollination of Non-native Coconut Palms, *Cocos nucifera* (Arecales: Arecaceae), by Non-native Madagascar Giant Day Geckos, *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis* (Sauria: Gekkonidae), in the Florida Keys. *Gekko* **5**: 33-38.
- Krysko, K.L., A.N. Hooper & C.M. III. Sheehy. (2003) The *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis* (Gray, 1970) (Sauria: Gekkonidae): a New established species. *Florida Scientist* **66** (3): 222-225.
- Ledoux, J.C. (2004) Araignées de l'île de La Réunion: I. Hahniidae, Ctenidae, Thomisidae et Clubionidae. *Revue Arachnologique* **14**: 159-191.
- Ledoux, J.C. (2007) Araignées de l'île de La Réunion : II. Salticidae (Araneae). *Revue Arachnologique* **17**: 9-34.
- Lever, C. (2003) *Naturalized Reptiles and Amphibians of the World*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, U.K, 338 pp.
- Martiré, D. & J. Rochat. (2008) *Les Papillons de la Réunion et leurs chenilles*. Biotope Edt, Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, 496 pp.
- Meshaka, W.E. (2011) *A Runaway Train in the Making: The Exotic Amphibians, Reptiles, Turtles, and Crocodilians of Florida*. Monograph 1. Herpetological Conservation and Biology **6**: 1-101.
- Minnaar, I.A., A. Köhler, C. Purchase & S.W. Nicolson. (2013) Coloured and Toxic Nectar: Feeding Choices of the Madagascar Giant Day Gecko, *Phelsuma grandis*. *Ethology* **119**: 417-426.
- Mozzi, R., G. Deso & J.-M. Probst. (2005) Un nouveau gecko vert introduit à La Réunion le *Phelsuma astriata semicarinata* (Cheke, 1982). *Bulletin Phaethon* **21**: 1-4.
- Norval, G., F.-Y. Lu, J.-J. Mao & K. Slater. (2012) It is not inside, it is on top! An example of vehicular-rafting by a house gecko (*Hemidactylus frenatus* Schlegel, 1836). *Herpetology Notes* **5**: 451-452.

- Probst, J.-M. (1997a) *Animaux de La Réunion - Guide d'identification des oiseaux, mammifères, reptiles et amphibiens*. Azalées Editions, Réunion, 168 pp.
- Probst, J.-M. (1997b) Contribution à la connaissance plus précise du milieu d'origine de quatre reptiles naturalisés à La Réunion avec une présentation des sous-espèces concernées. *Bulletin Phaethon* 6: 71-74.
- Probst, J.-M. (1999) Guide préliminaire des reptiles sédentaires de l'île de La Réunion et des îles éparses avec une liste des espèces migratrices et erratiques répertoriées depuis 10 ans. *Bulletin Phaethon* 10: 57-91.
- Probst, J.-M., A. Turpin, G. Deso, L. Albert, P. Brial & K. Abhaya. (2002) Un gecko vert devenant très envahissant : *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis* à La Réunion. *Bulletin Phaethon* 15: 46.
- Q-GIS (2013) Quantum-GIS, version 1.8.0-Lisboa.
- Quilici, S., M. Attié, F. Chiroleu, P. Ryckewaert, B. Reynaud, C. Guillermet, J. Poussereau, S. Ribes, R. Parnaudeau & S. Couteyen. (2002) Eléments pour une synthèse des connaissances sur l'entomofaune endémique des Hauts de La Réunion. Mission Parc National des Hauts de La Réunion / CIRAD / Insectarium de La Réunion / M.H.N. de La Réunion, 91 pp.
- Rocha, S., H. Rosler, P.S. Gehring, F. Glaw, D. Posada, D.J. Harris & M. Vences. (2010) Phylogenetic systematics of day geckos, genus *Phelsuma* based on molecular and morphological data (Squamata: Gekkonidae). *Zootaxa* 2429: 1-28.
- Rocha, S., M. Vences, F. Glaw, D. Posada & D.J. Harris. (2009) Multigene Phylogeny of Malagasy day geckos of the genus *Phelsuma*. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 52: 530-537.
- Sanchez, M. (2012) Le gecko vert de Bourbon, *Phelsuma borbonica* Mertens 1966, atlas de répartition, écologie et conservation. Nature Océan Indien unpublished report, La Réunion, 65 pp.
- Sanchez, M. (2013) Plan Régional de Lutte contre le grand gecko vert de Madagascar, *Phelsuma grandis* Gray 1870, sur l'île de La Réunion. Nature Océan Indien unpublished report, La Réunion, 54 pp.
- Sanchez, M. & A. Gandar. (2010a) Le grand gecko vert malgache, *Phelsuma grandis* Gray, 1870 (Squamata : Gekkonidae) introduit à Manapany-les-Bains : compte rendu des opérations visant à enrayer l'invasion. *Bulletin Phaethon* 30: 20-22.
- Sanchez, M. & A. Gandar. (2010b) Etat des lieux de la population introduite à Manapany-les-Bains du grand gecko vert malgache, *Phelsuma grandis* Gray 1870. Nature Océan Indien unpublished report, La Réunion, 26 pp.
- Sanchez, M. & J.-M. Probst. (2012) Présentation et clé de détermination des geckos verts du genre *Phelsuma* (Gray, 1825) de l'île de La Réunion (Squamata : Gekkonidae). *Cahiers Scientifiques de l'océan Indien occidental* 3: 11-17.
- Sanchez, M., J.-M. Probst & G. Deso. (2009) *Phelsuma inexpectata*, Mertens, 1966 (Sauria : Gekkonidae) sur l'île de La Réunion : Ecologie, répartition et menaces. *Bulletin de la Société Herpétologique de France* 132: 43-69.
- Strahm, W. (1996) Conservation of the flora of the Mascarene islands. *Curtis's Botanical Magazine* 13: 214-217.
- Strasberg, D., M. Rouget, D.M. Richardson, S. Baret, J. Dupont & R.M. Cowling (2005)

An assessment of habitat diversity, transformation and threats to biodiversity on Réunion Island (Mascarene Islands, Indian Ocean) as a basis for conservation planning. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 14 (12): 3015-3032.

- Tytle, T. (1992) Day geckos: *Phelsuma* The captive maintenance and propagation of day geckos. *Vivarium* 2: 15-19.
- Uetz, P. (2013) The Reptile Database. Available at: <http://www.reptile-database.org>. Last accessed on 5 September 2013.
- Van Heygen, E. (2004) The genus *Phelsuma* GRAY, 1825 on the Ampasindava peninsula, Madagascar. *Phelsuma* 12: 99-117.
- Wanger, T.C., I. Motzje, S.C. Furrer, B.W. Brook & B. Gruber. (2009a) How to monitor elusive lizards: comparison of capture–recapture methods on giant day geckos (Gekkonidae, *Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis*) in the Masoala rainforest exhibit, Zurich Zoo. *Ecological Research* 24: 345-353.
- Wanger, T.C., I. Motzje, S.C. Furrer & B. Gruber. (2009b) Movement patterns and habitat selection of the giant day gecko (*Phelsuma madagascariensis grandis*) in the Masoala rainforest exhibit, Zurich Zoo. *Salamandra* 45 (3): 147-153.

Appendix I

List of locality surveys during the study. Latitude and longitude are given in Universal Transverse of Mercator system (UTM, map datum: WGS84).

Locality	District	LAT.	LONG.	Elevation (m)	Research effort (min.)	n gecko	Cited by
Camp Magloire	POSSESSION	327770	7685147	10	20	0	—
Camp Magloire, Petite Ravine Lataniers	POSSESSION	327495	7684712	50	40	2	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	329082	7683402	110	45	0	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	328840	7683603	80	105	20	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	327216	7684006	20	20	0	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	327968	7683833	34	25	8	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	328327	7683790	60	40	9	—
Grande Ravine des Lataniers	POSSESSION	327338	7683935	35	45	4	—
Le vingt-huitième	POSSESSION	328327	7684890	160	60	0	—
Pépinière	POSSESSION	326858	7683773	27	20	0	—
Petite Ravine Lataniers	POSSESSION	328029	7684523	50	35	0	—
Petite Ravine Lataniers	POSSESSION	327064	7684186	32	25	0	—
Grande Montagne, résidence	POSSESSION	327200	7683820	37	20	0	—
Grande Ravine Lataniers, Rive Gauche	POSSESSION	327853	7683317	100	165	6	—
Commune Anglo, Arrêt Bus Paille en Queue	SAIN'T ANDRE	357667	7684890	10	20	0	—
Cascade Deltce	SAIN'T ANDRE	358278	7684408	36	20	0	—
Collège de Cambuston	SAIN'T ANDRE	359107	7685135	10	25	0	—
Collège des Milles Roches	SAIN'T ANDRE	359611	7680665	110	35	0	Probst et al., 2002
Hangar agricole Petit Etang	SAIN'T ANDRE	359684	7685747	5	45	1	—
Littoral de Cambuston, STEP	SAIN'T ANDRE	360540	7685871	0	20	0	—
Maison Tony, rue E. Thomas	SAIN'T ANDRE	359479	7684669	20	35	2	—
Parc du Colosse	SAIN'T ANDRE	360897	7685190	20	30	0	—
Quartier de Cambuston	SAIN'T ANDRE	359352	7685014	0	20	0	—
Rue des Saphirs	SAIN'T ANDRE	358123	7683596	100	20	0	—
Chemin des Palmiers Royals	SAIN'T BENOIT	365357	7673873	50	20	4	—
La Marine, Bourbier	SAIN'T BENOIT	365518	7674368	10	60	0	—
La Marine, Bourbier	SAIN'T BENOIT	365528	7674359	0	55	0	—
La Montagne, Chemin de la Vigie	SAIN'T DENIS	336365	7689919	345	25	0	Probst et al., 2002
Chemin Grand Canal	SAIN'T DENIS	343209	7687068	120	35	1	—

Locality	District	LAT.	LONG.	Elevation (m)	Research effort (min.)	n gecko	Cited by
Grande Montée	SAINT DENIS	346670	7685361	250	60	1	—
Grande Montée	SAINT DENIS	346480	7685272	230	20	1	—
La Bretagne, Eglise	SAINT DENIS	343361	7684905	310	40	0	—
Montgaillard	SAINT DENIS	340342	7688034	120	20	1	—
Parc de la Providence	SAINT DENIS	339373	7688270	47	40	0	Probst et al., 2002
La Montagne, Résidence	SAINT DENIS	336822	7689559	405	20	0	Probst et al., 2002
La Montagne, Résidence	SAINT DENIS	335458	7689388	354	30	0	Probst et al., 2002
La Montagne, Rue des Pétrels	SAINT DENIS	334659	7689345	270	20	0	—
Rue Montgaillard	SAINT DENIS	340336	7688015	130	30	1	—
Piton Saint Leu, le Plateau	SAINT LEU	326164	7651648	310	20	8	—
Cambaie, résidence	SAINT PAUL	323305	7681023	57	60	3	—
Cambaie, zone industrielle	SAINT PAUL	322995	7681227	50	30	0	—
Bellemène	SAINT PAUL	322808	7674592	370	20	1	—
Bellemène	SAINT PAUL	322928	7674652	350	25	2	—
Bellemène	SAINT PAUL	323081	7674521	370	45	10	—
Bellemène, amont du Chemin Lougnon	SAINT PAUL	322698	7675040	290	25	0	—
Bellemène r	SAINT PAUL	323183	7674494	380	30	0	—
Bellemène, Chemin Lougnon	SAINT PAUL	322499	7675174	230	30	0	—
Bellemène, école catholique	SAINT PAUL	322991	7674509	380	25	0	—
Cambaie résidence	SAINT PAUL	323474	7681094	10	70	16	—
La Saline	SAINT PAUL	315682	7668031	0	40	2	—
La Saline, bord de mer	SAINT PAUL	315785	7667578	0	60	0	—
La Saline, école primaire	SAINT PAUL	315715	7668477	5	50	0	—
La Saline, Casino	SAINT PAUL	315456	7669043	0	20	0	—
Rue Pothier, Vieux Plongeur	SAINT PAUL	321077	7676436	0	60	0	—
Condé, Ancienne National	SAINT PIERRE	345066	7644165	390	55	1	—
Condé, Ancienne National	SAINT PIERRE	345795	7645052	460	20	0	—
IUT de Terre Sainte, Nord	SAINT PIERRE	343372	7639437	45	55	0	—
IUT de Terre Sainte, Sud	SAINT PIERRE	343531	7639305	60	55	0	—
Allée coco	SAINTE MARIE	347312	7684401	320	40	5	—
Allée coco, aval	SAINTE MARIE	347232	7684843	280	30	0	—
La Ressource, Chemin des Evis	SAINTE MARIE	346968	7684491	280	20	0	—
La Ressource les Hauts	SAINTE MARIE	347304	7684358	320	60	3	—

Locality	District	LAT.	LONG.	Elevation (m)	Research effort (min.)	n gecko	Cited by
Le Verger, Allée Coco	SAINTE MARIE	347144	7683852	390	50	0	—
Ravine des Figues	SAINTE MARIE	347807	7684917	260	25	0	—
Littoral Ste Marie, médiathèque	SAINTE MARIE	349220	7688726	0	30	0	—
Chemin Marencourt, Cascade Niagara	SAINTE SUZANNE	356135	7686379	10	30	2	—
Commune Ango	SAINTE SUZANNE	355423	7682209	180	20	1	—
Commune Ango	SAINTE SUZANNE	354471	7681914	278	20	0	—
Embouchure Rivière Sainte Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	356216	7687105	0	75	1	—
Amont Rivière Saint Jean	SAINTE SUZANNE	356821	7683033	157	30	0	—
Pointe Canal	SAINTE SUZANNE	352767	7683815	300	20	0	—
Bassin Bœuf, aval	SAINTE SUZANNE	352984	7683528	317	35	0	—
Bagatelle, sommet de ravine	SAINTE SUZANNE	352982	7684404	260	55	0	—
Bagatelle, sommet de ravine	SAINTE SUZANNE	352980	7684405	270	30	0	—
Bagatelle, sommet de ravine	SAINTE SUZANNE	353180	7684692	250	20	0	—
Grand Rivière Saint Jean	SAINTE SUZANNE	355906	7681816	210	20	0	—
Camp des Evis, Arrêt Bus Pablo Neruda	SAINTE SUZANNE	357750	7683780	90	20	0	—
Camp Hazier	SAINTE SUZANNE	353804	7687621	60	30	0	—
Cascade Délice, Est	SAINTE SUZANNE	358200	7684420	34	20	0	—
Cascade Délice, Ouest	SAINTE SUZANNE	357799	7684462	44	30	0	—
Cascade Niagara	SAINTE SUZANNE	354927	7686019	20	30	4	—
Chemin Marencourt, Cascade Niagara	SAINTE SUZANNE	355663	7686383	10	20	7	—
Commune Ango	SAINTE SUZANNE	356764	7683720	120	40	0	—
Commune Ango les Bas	SAINTE SUZANNE	357674	7684886	15	50	1	—
Commune Ango, Arrêt de Bus Longani	SAINTE SUZANNE	356135	7683432	165	20	0	—
Commune Carron, Bellevue	SAINTE SUZANNE	355584	7684351	150	30	2	—
Commune Carron, Bellevue	SAINTE SUZANNE	354914	7684138	230	30	1	—
Deux Rives	SAINTE SUZANNE	356304	7682335	176	30	0	—
Étang de Bois Rouge	SAINTE SUZANNE	359022	7686669	0	20	2	—
Front de mer de Sainte Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	354910	7687913	0	20	4	—
Grande Montée	SAINTE SUZANNE	353793	7685310	160	25	2	—
Hauts de Bellevue, ruisseau la Vigne	SAINTE SUZANNE	354635	7683646	250	60	0	—
Hauts de Bellevue, ruisseau la Vigne	SAINTE SUZANNE	354699	7683735	240	30	0	—
La Liberté	SAINTE SUZANNE	354823	7684667	190	20	5	—
La Liberté	SAINTE SUZANNE	354530	7684032	230	20	0	—

Locality	District	LAT.	LONG.	Elevation (m)	Research effort (min.)	n gecko	Cited by
La Liberté	SAINTE SUZANNE	354183	7683876	270	20	0	—
La Liberté	SAINTE SUZANNE	355021	7684661	180	30	4	—
La Marine	SAINTE SUZANNE	357079	7687070	0	40	0	—
L'Espérance	SAINTE SUZANNE	355176	7682435	190	30	2	—
Littoral Sainte Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	354238	7688290	40	35	2	—
Littoral Camp Hazier, temple Tamoul	SAINTE SUZANNE	353069	7688528	20	20	0	—
Littoral de Sainte Suzanne, SDIS	SAINTE SUZANNE	355363	7687700	0	20	1	—
Mairie annexe Saint Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	358041	7685172	7	55	2	—
Niagara, Renaissance	SAINTE SUZANNE	355057	7685521	52	20	1	—
Petite Rivière Saint Jean	SAINTE SUZANNE	355997	7682646	140	40	0	—
Bel Air	SAINTE SUZANNE	353767	7686922	90	20	0	—
Jacque Cargot	SAINTE SUZANNE	353926	7686388	110	30	0	—
Résidentiel de Bagatelle	SAINTE SUZANNE	352574	7685180	560	25	0	—
Radier Rivière Sainte Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	353725	7684845	200	50	2	—
Ravine du centre d'enfouissement	SAINTE SUZANNE	354287	7686595	90	30	0	—
Rivière Sainte Suzanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	353616	7684704	165	40	1	—
Route	SAINTE SUZANNE	357170	7685745	0	25	9	—
Ruisseau Marie Jeanne	SAINTE SUZANNE	353354	7683911	290	25	0	—
Usine de Bois Rouge, stade	SAINTE SUZANNE	358740	7686740	0	20	5	—
Bois Rouge, Temple Tamoul	SAINTE SUZANNE	357676	7686478	0	20	7	—
Clinique Durieux	TAMPON	345574	7647007	570	35	0	—
Clinique Durieux	TAMPON	345129	7646690	510	30	1	—
Impasse du père Maunier	TAMPON	345817	7647480	605	55	0	—
La Chatoire	TAMPON	345403	7646595	520	30	0	—
Résidence Fushia	TAMPON	345196	7646788	515	20	3	—
Université du Tampon	TAMPON	345245	7647209	540	30	3	—
Université du Tampon	TAMPON	345113	7647086	550	40	2	—
Université du Tampon, impasse Archambaud	TAMPON	345419	7647444	570	40	2	—
Chemin des Mirabelles	PETITE ILE	351832	7638295	340	135	2	—